

**“A CROSS SECTIONAL STUDY OF ASSOCIATION OF
FUNDUS MANIFESTATIONS WITH THE SERUM LIPID
PROFILE IN HYPERTENSIVE PATIENTS.”**

By

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

χ^2	Chi square
AION	Anterior ischemic optic neuropathy
BRVO	Branch retinal vein occlusion
CRAO	Central retinal artery occlusion
CRVO	Central retinal vein occlusion
FBS	Fasting blood sugar
HDL	High density lipoprotein
IHD	Ischemic heart disease
LDL	Low density lipoprotein
TIA	Transient Ischemic Attack
VLDL	Very low density lipoprotein

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVES

Dyslipidemia in hypertensive patients may act as a predisposing risk factor, an aggravating or complicating factor. This study aims to assess the association between concentrations of various serum lipids, lipoproteins and retinal changes in patients with hypertension.

METHODS

The cross sectional study was conducted at B.L.D.E.U'S ShriB.M.Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research centre, Bijapur from 1st October 2012- 31st March 2014. A total of 245 patients were included in the study who were diagnosed to have primary essential hypertension. All patients were evaluated in detail regarding hypertensive status and detailed ophthalmic evaluation was done.

Patients were divided into retinopathy group and no retinopathy group initially. Further retinopathy patients were divided depending on the severity of the retinopathy into GRADE I, II, III & IV.

RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS

Of the 245 patients, 106 patients had normal fundus and 139 patients had retinopathy. Among these patients 91 were males and 48 were females. With M:F=1.9:1 with the age range of 25-85 years (Mean age of 57.16 years). And average duration of hypertension of 7.55.

The correlation of severity of hypertension with retinopathy was statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$) and the relationship between retinopathy and duration was also statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$).

The increased level of total cholesterol correlated well with increasing severity of retinopathy. LDL cholesterol and Triglyceride levels correlated positively with

increasing severity of retinopathy which was statistically significant.($p < 0.0001$)

CONCLUSION

Our study demonstrated an association between serum lipid parameters and the prevalence of hypertensive retinopathy. Dyslipidemia is already considered as important risk factor for end organ failure and it can be considered as risk factor for severity of retinopathy. Preservation of vision may be an additional motivating factor for lowering serum lipid levels in persons with hypertension in whom they are elevated.

Key words: Dyslipidemia; Essential hypertension, Hypertensive Retinopathy

INTRODUCTION

Systemic hypertension (140/90 mm hg and above) is present in 25% urban (34 million) and 10% rural (31.5 million) subjects in India.^{1,2}

High blood pressure is related with many clinical complications such as stroke, cardiac failure, myocardial infarction, renal failure, peripheral vascular diseases.³ Retinopathy is considered one of the indicators of target organ damage.

Hypertensive retinopathy is among the vascular complications of essential hypertension. It is known that the auto regulation of the retinal circulation fails as bloodpressure increases beyond a critical limit.

However, elevated blood pressure alone doesnot fully account for the extent of retinopathy. There are cases in which retinopathy wasresolved despite the persistence of high blood pressure. In addition to the effect of highblood pressure, other factors and humoral components probably take part in thepathogenesis of hypertensive retinopathy.⁴

Hyperlipidemia contributes to the process of arteriosclerosis, which develops even faster in the presence of hypertension or diabetes mellitus. Hyperlipidemia or dyslipidemia is known to be an important risk factor inhypertensive patients.^{5,6,7}

Although atherosclerotic changes were described in retinal arteries half a centuryago (then called arteriosclerotic or arteriolosclerotic), there are no data on lipoproteinsand retinal artery atherosclerosis.⁸

Dyslipidemiais known to be a risk factor for retinopathy and other ocularabnormalities. When it is associated with diseases like diabetes, hypertension theoutcome is complicated. Its role in association with diabetic retinopathy and age relatedmaculopathy is well proven.^{9,10}

Dyslipidemia in hypertensive patients may act as a predisposing risk factor, anaggravating or complicating factor.⁷

An understanding of various ocular manifestations, spectrum of findings and their association with components of lipid profile (LDL, HDL, VLDL, Total Cholesterol, and Triglycerides) may be helpful in risk stratification and intailoring of anti-hypertensive and lipid lowering treatment.

Ophthalmoscopic findings are helpful in evaluating the duration, severity, predictions or hypertension vasculopathy effects.³

Hence this study aims to assess the association between concentrations of various serum lipids, lipoproteins and retinal changes in patients with hypertension.

AIM AND OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. To evaluate fundus findings, and to correlate findings with the components of lipid profile (LDL, HDL, VLDL total cholesterol and triglycerides) in hypertensive patients.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Hypertension may be defined as “the level of which the benefits (minus the risks and costs) of action exceeds the risks and costs (minus the benefits) of inaction.”¹¹

As per the JNC VII report on prevention detection, evaluation and treatment of high B.P.^{12x}

Category	Systolic BP (mm Hg)	Diastolic BP (mm Hg)
Normal	< 120	< 80
Pre hypertension	120-139	80-89
Stage 1	140-159	90-99
Stage 2	> 160	>100

Optimal BP with respect to cardiovascular risk is < 120 mm Hg systolic and < 80 mm Hg diastolic. Based on the average of two or more readings taken at each of two or more visits after an initial screening.

Essential hypertension [primary hypertension]

Essential hypertension is the name given to a group of persons whose arterial pressures are raised and in whom no specific disease can be found to account for the raised pressure. It is thus diagnosed by exclusion. Its clinical manifestations represent the consequences of raised arterial pressure on the cardiovascular system. The end stages of essential hypertension are a comparatively uniform malignant course dominated by Fibrinoid necrosis of arterioles, and much more benign course in which the other vascular lesions play a dominant role.

Clinical features of essential hypertension¹¹

Age of onset

Since vascular disease is a consequence of advancing age, most patients with essential hypertension presenting with symptoms of benign phase belong to later agegroups.

Symptoms

The majority of patients with hypertension has no specific symptoms referable to their blood pressure elevation and will be identified only in the course of physical examination

Headache: is characteristic only of severe hypertension commonly localized to occipital region. Usually present when patient awakens in morning subsides spontaneously after several hours.

Other possible related complaints include

- Dizziness
- Palpitation
- Easy fatigability
- Impotence

Complaints referable to vascular disease include:

- Epistaxis
- Hematuria
- Blurring of vision due to retinal changes
- Dizziness due to TIA
- Angina and dyspnoea due to cardiac failure.

Clinical evaluation of essential hypertension

A strong family history of hypertension along with the intermittent finding of elevated pressure in the past favours the diagnosis of hypertension. Exclude the cause of secondary hypertension.

Elicit risk factors: Smoking, Diabetes, Renal disorders. Assess patients' life style: Diet, Physical activity, family status, and work.

Physical examination

Starts with general appearance: Round face and truncal obesity – Cushing syndrome. Is muscular development of upper extremities out of proportion to lower limb - Coarctation of Aorta. Compare the BP and pulse in both extremities and in supine and standing. Measure patients height and weight. Fundus examination because this provides clues to the duration and prognosis of hypertension. Palpation and auscultation of carotid arteries for evidence of stenosis or occlusion.

Examination of cardia

For evidence of left ventricular hypertrophy and cardiac decompensation

For left ventricular lift

For 3rd and 4th heart sounds

Examination of lungs

For pulmonary rales

Extra cardiac murmurs and palpable collateral vessels as seen in Coarctation of aorta

Examination of abdomen

Auscultation for bruits originating in stenotic renal arteries. These have diastolic components, best heard just right or left of midline, above umbilicus. Palpation for aneurysms and enlarged kidneys.

Examination of extremities for edema

Search for evidence of previous CVA

Laboratory investigations¹³

These are divided into those, which should be performed in all patients, with sustained hypertension (Basic studies) and those, which should be added if From the initial evaluation a secondary form of hypertension is suggested Arterial pressure is not controlled after initial therapy / (secondary studies)

Basic studies

a. Always included

- Urine for protein, sugar, and blood, Microscopy.
- Hematocrit
- Serum creatinine, blood urea, serum electrolytes
- Fasting blood glucose
- Total cholesterol
- ECG

b. Usually included

- TSH
- WBC counts
- Fasting lipid profile
- Serum uric acid
- Chest X-ray
- Echocardiogram

Special studies to screen for secondary hypertension:

Renovascular disease: ACE inhibitor radio nucleotide renal scan

Renal duplex Doppler flow studies

MR angiographies

Pheochromocytoma: 24 hour's urine for creatinine, metanephrines and catecholamines. Cushing's syndrome: Overnight dexamethasone suppression test or 24 hours urine cortisol and creatinine Primary aldosteronism Plasma aldosterone and rennin activity ratio.

Complications of untreated hypertension [End organ damage in hypertension]

The adverse effects of hypertension principally involve the CNS, the retina, the heart, and kidneys.

CNS

Stroke

When this results from cerebral hemorrhage and cerebral ischaemia it is a common complication of hypertension and a major cause of death. Cerebral ischaemia is secondary to atherosclerosis. Cerebral hemorrhage is the result of both elevated arterial pressure and development of micro aneurysms called Charcot – Bouchard aneurysm.

Hypertensive encephalopathy¹³

This is a rare condition characterized by very high blood pressure and neurological symptoms including transient disturbances of speech, or vision, paraesthesia, disorientation, seizures and loss of consciousness. Papilloedema is common. Neurological deficit is reversible if hypertension is treated.

Heart

Most deaths due to hypertension results from, myocardial infarction / congestive heart failure. In short raised pressure lead to¹⁴. Myocyte hypertrophy, interstitial changes and fibrosis Reduction in flow in intracardiac vessels and endothelial dysfunction – small vessel disease. Epicardial (large vessel) coronary disease Increased peripheral resistance and loss of compliance in arteries.

Kidney¹³

Atherosclerotic lesions of the afferent and efferent arterioles and the glomerular capillary tufts are the most common renal vascular lesions in hypertension and results in a decreased glomerular filtration rate and tubular dysfunction. Proteinuria and microscopic hematuria occur because of glomerular lesions and approximately 10% of the deaths caused by hypertension results from renal failure. Blood loss in hypertension occurs not only from renal lesions. Epistaxis hemoptysis and metrorrhagia also occur frequently in these patients.

HYPERTENSIVE RETINOPATHY

Hypertensive retinopathy is a condition characterized by a spectrum of retinal vascular signs in people with elevated blood pressure.¹⁵ The detection of hypertensive retinopathy with the use of an ophthalmoscope has long been regarded as part of the standard evaluation of persons with hypertension.¹⁶

This clinical practice is supported by both previous¹⁷ and current¹⁸ reports of the Joint National Committee on Prevention, Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Pressure (JNC), which list retinopathy as one of several markers of target-organ damage in hypertension.

On the basis of the JNC criteria, the presence of retinopathy may be an indication for initiating antihypertensive treatment, even in people with stage 1

hypertension (blood pressure, 140 to 159/90 to 99 mm Hg) who have no other evidence of target-organ damage.

Pathophysiology

The retinal circulation undergoes a series of pathophysiological changes in response to elevated blood pressure.¹⁹ In the initial, vasoconstrictive stage, there is vasospasm and an increase in retinal arteriolar tone owing to local autoregulatory mechanisms. This stage is seen clinically as a generalized narrowing of the retinal arterioles. Persistently elevated blood pressure leads to intimal thickening, hyperplasia of the media wall, and hyaline degeneration in the subsequent, sclerotic, stage. This stage corresponds to more severe generalized and focal areas of arteriolar narrowing, changes in the arteriolar and venular junctions (i.e., arteriovenous nicking or nipping), and alterations in the arteriolar light reflex (i.e., widening and accentuation of the central light reflex, or "copper wiring").

This is followed by an exudative stage, in which there is disruption of the blood-retina barrier, necrosis of the smooth muscles and endothelial cells, exudation of blood and lipids, and retinal ischemia. These changes are manifested in the retina as microaneurysms, hemorrhages, hard exudates, and cotton-wool spots. Swelling of the optic disk may occur at this time and usually indicates severely elevated blood pressure (i.e., malignant hypertension). Because better methods for the control of blood pressure are now available in the general population, malignant hypertension is rarely seen.

In contrast, other retinal vascular complications of hypertension, such as macroaneurysms and branch-vein occlusions, are not uncommon in patients with chronically elevated blood pressure. The stages of hypertensive retinopathy described, however, may not be sequential. For example, signs of retinopathies that reflect the

exudative stage, such as retinal hemorrhage or microaneurysms, may be seen in eyes that do not have features of the sclerotic stage (e.g., arteriovenous nicking). The exudative signs are nonspecific, since they are seen in diabetes and other conditions.

CLINICAL ASPECTS

Retinal vascular response and other retinal changes seen in hypertension are variable and depend on several factors. The most important factors are the rate and degree of hypertension and the baseline condition of the retinal vasculature. Concomitant diseases, such as diabetes or renal or connective tissue disorders also play a role in the severity of findings.

- Clinical findings seen in the retinal vasculature in hypertensive retinopathy
- include the following:²⁰
- Arteriolar narrowing (focal and diffuse)
- Arteriovenous crossing changes
- Arterial tortuosity
- Arterial sclerosis
- Increased branching angles

One of the earliest and classic signs of hypertensive retinopathy is arteriolar narrowing. An increase in vascular wall tone initiated acutely by autoregulatory mechanisms causes a decrease in caliber of the vessel, in what has been described as the vasoconstrictive phase.¹⁹ A more focal or diffuse vasoconstrictive state may be observed, depending on the initial condition of the retinal vasculature. Vessels with areas of sclerosis lack muscle tone and tend to dilate secondary to elevated intraluminal pressure.

Nonsclerotic vessels exhibit narrowing because of intact muscular walls and preserved autoregulatory response. Hayreh and colleagues,²¹ in comparing prehypertensive fluorescein fundus angiograms to those with hypertensive retinopathy, found nonnarrowing of arterioles. They concluded that the apparent narrowing was caused by an ophthalmoscopic artifact produced by retinal edema masking the arteriole walls from the sides along with the contrast of dilated venules, which made the arterioles appear more tapered.

Clinical findings in hypertensive retinopathy are:²²

- Hemorrhages
- Retinal and macular edema
- Edema residues (hard exudates)
- Inner retinal ischemic spots (cotton-wool spots)
- Nerve fiber layer loss
- Focal intraretinal periarteriolar transudates (FIPTs)

Hemorrhages

One common feature is hemorrhage. Hemorrhages within the more superficial layers of the inner retina have a flame-shaped appearance because they track along axons in the nerve fiber layer. Deeper hemorrhages in the retina have a dot or blot appearance, which varies with the configuration of the neural elements of layer to which they are confined.

Hayreh and associates²⁰ concluded that retinal hemorrhages were only a minor feature of hypertensive retinopathy. They found that nerve fiber layer hemorrhages in the distribution of the radial peripapillary capillaries were more common than dot or blot hemorrhages or subhyaloid hemorrhages. This probably reflects the arteriolar character of the radial peripapillary capillary bed. Hard exudates,

cotton-wool spots, and retinal edema are additional manifestations of the exudate phase of hypertensive retinopathy and indicate a more serious stage of the disease.

Hard exudates

Hard exudates or, more appropriately, edema residues are formed from extravasated plasma during the exudative phase. The residues are composed of lipids and cholesterol, giving them a characteristic waxy yellow or glistening appearance, and seem to settle in a bathtub ring-like configuration. They generally are found in the posterior pole and assume patterns that reflect the source of the leakage (i.e., circinate rings) and the neural elements of the layer in which they are found (i.e., macular star).²⁰

Retinal and macular edema

The development of clinical edema of the retina and macula may stem from a variety of events at a cellular level and may have multiple causes. Loss of autoregulation, as in episodes of acute hypertension, may result in an increase in transmural pressure in the capillaries leading to transudation of plasma into surrounding retina producing extracellular edema. Intracellular edema is the direct result of retinal ischemia. Breakdown of the retinal pigment epithelium (RPE) blood–retinal barrier secondary to hypertensive choroidopathy produces serous retinal detachments overlying regions of

choroidal ischemia. Diffusion of subretinal fluid into the retina eventually may create tissue edema.

Cotton-wool spots

Cotton-wool spots, or so-called soft exudates, are areas of acute inner retinal ischemia caused by occlusion of terminal arterioles. They have a fluffy white appearance, irregular borders, and most commonly are found in the posterior pole and

along the distribution of the radial peripapillary capillary bed. They are localized within the nerve fiber layer, often involving the underlying ganglion cells and inner nuclear while sparing the deeper retinal layers. Fluorescein angiography demonstrates nonperfusion of the cotton-wool spots and adjacent capillaries. Typically, they resolve ophthalmoscopically in 4 to 6 weeks, leaving a corresponding nerve fiber layer defect.

Focal intraretinal periarteriolar transudates (FIPTs)

Cases of accelerated hypertension often are manifest by FIPTs. These appear as dull-white round, focal areas surrounding arterioles. The proposed mechanism of FIPT formation is the focal breakdown of the blood-retinal barrier, with the accumulation of plasma deposits in the retina following an accelerated hypertension event.²²

ARTERIOSCLEROTIC CHANGES

Sclerotic changes are observed within the vessel walls as constriction of the retinal vasculature persists. The arteriole wall normally is invisible, appearing only as an erythrocyte column with central light reflex by ophthalmoscopy. As the wall thickens from continuous vasoconstriction, the light reflex becomes more diffuse and partially

obscures the blood column, giving the once transparent arteriole a yellowed or copperwire appearance. Progression of the thickening and sclerotic changes eventually obscures the blood column completely, producing a silver wire appearance. Along with reflective changes, the thickening produces arteriovenous crossing changes. Retinal arterioles and venules share a common adventitial sheath at their crossing points. As the arteriolar wall thickens, the venule appears tapered if posterior to the arteriole or elevated if over the arteriole. Other characteristic changes common but not unique to arteriosclerosis are increased tortuosity secondary to fibrous

replacement of the vessel wall and increased arteriolar branching angles, known as perpendicularization. Progression of arteriosclerosis leads to endothelial damage and necrosis of the muscular component of the vessel walls.

This leads to a breakdown of the blood–retinal barrier, causing exudative leakage into the retina. The formation of fibrin and thrombosis within the vessel may cause closure of the lumen, resulting in ischemic changes within the retina. This has been described as the exudative phase. Concomitant choroidopathy may contribute to further retinal changes seen in this phase of hypertensive retinopathy.²⁰

- Complications related to hypertensive retinopathy include the following:
 - Central or branch artery occlusion
 - Central or branch vein occlusion
 - Macroaneurysms
 - Epiretinal membrane
 - Neovascularization
 - Vitreous hemorrhage
 - Cystoid macular edema

Artery and vein occlusions and macroaneurysms are the most common results of arteriosclerotic changes found in this condition. The development of neovascularization with or without vitreous hemorrhage is the result of subsequent retinal ischemia. Cystoid macular edema also may result from ischemia, as well as from the breakdown of the retinal vascular and RPE blood barrier.

Epiretinal membranes may form in the cicatricial phase of any of these events. Consequent development of a full macular hole after severe hypertensive retinopathy with macular edema and vitreous hemorrhage also has been described. Other recent findings have shown abnormal electroretinogram and visually evoked potential studies 2 to 4 years after an accelerated hypertensive event likely related to retinal infarction and ischemic optic neuropathy, respectively.²⁰

The overall rates of hypertensive retinopathy in the nondiabetic population range from 0.8% to 7.8%.²³ The study of populations is difficult and highly variable because of different evaluation methods, grading classifications of retinopathy, selection bias groups, and the association of other systemic diseases.

HYPERTENSIVE CHOROIDOPATHY

The choroid is very sensitive to blood pressure changes that only indirectly affect the overlying RPE and neurosensory retina. Its pathophysiologic response to arterial blood pressure changes also is very different than that of the retinal vasculature. The choroid receives sympathetic innervation and is sensitive to circulating vasoconstrictive factors such as angiotensin II, adrenaline, and vasopressin. These factors and neural stimulation can initiate vasoconstriction of the choroid and choriocapillaris, leading to focal ischemia. The overlying RPE and the outer blood–retinal barrier may be compromised as a result.

The clinical features of hypertensive choroidopathy include the following:²⁰

- Elshnig's spots and Siegrist's spots (RPE and choroidal infarcts)
- Subretinal exudates
- Serous retinal detachments
- RPE depigmentation (chronic)
- Choroidal sclerosis

Clinically, direct changes to the choroidal vasculature are difficult to detect by ophthalmoscopy. Many findings seen as retinal changes are a result of choroidal vasculature response to blood pressure change. Elschnig's spots are ischemic infarcts of the RPE that coincide to hypoperfusion of the underlying choroid. They appear as focal subretinal lesions with yellowish halo. In an experimental model, Elschnig's spots appeared within 24 hours of accelerated hypertension. Ischemic infarcts at the equator have a more linear appearance and are referred to as Siegrist's streaks.

The presence of Siegrist's streaks may indicate a more advanced vascular sclerosis. As ischemic RPE becomes edematous, the blood-retinal barrier becomes disrupted, allowing leakage of fluid from the choroid into the subretinal space and forming serous detachments. Resolution of such detachments can follow rapidly the restoration of blood pressure control. Over time, the Elschnig's spots and areas of serous detachment develop central areas of pigmentation with surrounding atrophy. Sclerotic choroidal vessels become visible through areas of atrophic RPE.

In malignant hypertension, one of the earliest changes seen is optic nerve head edema. Clinical Findings in Neuropathy

- Optic disc edema
- Optic disc pallor
- Optic disc ischemia

The clinical appearance is indistinguishable from other causes of optic nerve head swelling, such as elevated intracranial pressure. The mechanism of disc swelling remains controversial. Kishi and associates²³ demonstrated axonal hydropic swelling that was secondary to ischemia. They later concluded that the ischemia produced was related to vasoconstriction of the peripapillary choroidal and optic nerve head vessels.

The direct vasoconstrictive and occlusive properties seen in hypertensive choroidopathy lead to ischemic changes in the optic nerve head because it receives most of its blood supply from the peripapillarychoroidal vessels. Further, vascular endothelial substances can diffuse easily into the optic nerve head from the surrounding choroidal bed and cause vasoconstriction of the optic nerve head vessels.^{23,24}

CLASSIFICATION OF HYPERTENSIVE RETINOPATHY²⁰

Since Marcus Gunn's description in 1898 of the changes in retinal vessels in patients with arterial hypertension, various classification systems have been attempted to explain observed changes and correlate them with the systemic disease. The first major classification scheme, by Keith and colleagues, was designed to relate survival to retinal vascular changes in the hypertensive population. Patients are classified according to the severity of their fundus changes into four groups and morbidity is looked at over a 5-year period. They found that changes correlated directly with the degree of systemic hypertension and, inversely, with the prognosis for survival. Later, Wagener and coworkers developed more quantitative criteria for classifying hypertensive retinal vascular changes.

This system was based on the narrowing of arterioles and graded focal arterial constriction. In addition, they grouped vascular hypertension with associated retinal changes within each group. Although more precise in design, reproducibility of the system was poor, and it was soon replaced by a more complete classification scheme described by Harold Scheie in 1953. He graded changes of hypertension and arteriolar sclerosis separately in five stages. He defined hypertensive changes as those related to arteriolar constriction and vascular changes from long-standing hypertension as arteriolar sclerosis.

Keith-Wagener-Barker Classification¹⁵

Group	Description
1	Mild to moderate narrowing and sclerosis of the arteries
2	Moderate to marked sclerosis of the retinal arterioles; exaggeration of the light reflex; arteriovenous compression changes or generalized or localized narrowing of the arterioles
3	Retinal arteriolar narrowing and focal constriction; retinal edema; cotton-wool spots; hemorrhage
4	Group 3 plus papilledema

Wagener-Clay-Gipner Modification of Generalized Arteriolar Narrowing¹⁵

Group	Description
1.	Reduction of caliber of arterioles to three fourths of average caliber
2.	Reduction of caliber of arterioles to half of average caliber
3.	Reduction of caliber of arterioles to one third of average caliber
4.	Arterioles thread-like or invisible

Scheie Classification¹⁵

Group	Hypertension	Arteriolar Sclerosis
0	No change	
1	Barely detectable arteriolar narrowing	Barely detectable light reflex changes
2	Obvious arteriolar narrowing with focal irregularities	Obvious increased light reflex changes
3	Grade 2 plus retinal hemorrhages or exudates	Copper wire arterioles
4	Grade 3 plus papilledema	Silver wire arteriole.

One of the problems that complicates all classification systems is the ophthalmoscopic variation in the extent of the acute hypertensive changes and those of the duration-related sclerotic changes observed in the same patient. In 1957, Leishmann presented a seven-part classification that took into account the development of arteriolar sclerosis as part of the natural aging process and emphasized the modified ability of retinal arterioles with involutional sclerosis to respond to hypertension. Subsequent to these discussions, clinicians have become sensitive to the need to account for the presence or absence of arteriolar sclerosis in interpreting the fundi of hypertensive patients. In 1966, the original study by Keith and associates was updated and modified to include the grading of generalized and focal arteriolar narrowing and arteriolar sclerosis. This modified system served as a helpful prognosticator of hypertensive disease. Arteriolar narrowing and focal constrictions in the absence of retinal hemorrhages or disc edema seem to be the most sensitive indicators employed by the system. It currently remains the most commonly used classification for grouping hypertensive patients ophthalmoscopically⁹.

Blood Pressure

In many studies it has been proved that there is a strong association between presence of hypertensive retinopathy and elevated blood pressure.²⁵⁻²⁹

In elevated hypertension there is occurrence of specific retinal signs which is confirmed in few studies.^{30,31} Other signs of retinopathy like focal arteriolar narrowing, retinal hemorrhages, microaneurysms and cotton-wool spots were related to current blood pressure levels.^{30,31} Hyperglycemia, inflammation and endothelial dysfunction may also be involved in pathogenesis of retinopathy.³²

The Risk of Stroke

In a Population-based study by Wisconsin³³ and in Japan³⁴, have shown that the risks of fatal and nonfatal stroke are higher in persons with signs of retinopathy. The Atherosclerosis Risk in Communities study, showed that some signs of retinopathy (e.g., retinal hemorrhages, microaneurysms, and cotton-wool spots) were associated with a risk of newly diagnosed clinical stroke that was two to four times as high as that for patients who did not have these signs, even when the analysis was controlled for the effects of long-term elevations in blood pressure, cigarette smoking, elevated lipid levels, and other risk factors for stroke.³⁵

The Risk of Coronary Heart Disease

There are only few studies regarding the association of hypertensive retinopathy and the risk of coronary heart disease. In the National Health Examination Survey, persons with retinal arteriolar narrowing, as detected on ophthalmoscopy, were more likely to have preexisting coronary heart disease as those without these changes, after the analysis was controlled for the presence or absence of hypertension and diabetes and for serum cholesterol levels.³⁶ In a study of 560 men with hypertension and hyperlipidemia, the presence of hypertensive retinopathy predicted a

doubling of the risk of coronary heart disease, and the presence of either generalized or focal narrowing of the arterioles predicted almost a three times risk ³⁷

Associated factors

Less than half the retinal changes associated with hypertension cannot be explained by high blood pressure. The low sensitivity of retinal abnormalities associated with hypertension indicates that hypertensive retinopathy is not common in hypertensive people. In both the Beaver Dam eye study and the Blue Mountains eye study little difference was found in the presence of haemorrhages and exudates between normotensive and hypertensive people aged over 65.

Various other conditions have been associated with hypertensive retinopathy, such as

1. Ethnicity,³⁸
2. Smoking,⁴¹⁻⁴³
3. Intima-media thickness,^{41,42}
4. Carotid plaque score,⁴²
5. Carotid artery stiffness,
6. Serum cholesterol concentration,^{41,36,43}
7. Diabetes,^{36,43}
8. Body mass index.^{36,43}

SERUM LIPIDS AND RETINOPATHY

Studies have shown that with increasing severity of hypertension, the prevalence of elevated total cholesterol, LDL cholesterol and low HDL cholesterol was higher.⁷

According to the American Heart Association guidelines, blood pressure < 130/85 mmHg; total cholesterol < 200 mg/dl; triglycerides < 200 mg/dl; HDL > 40 mg/dl and LDL < 130 g/dl, are favourable risk factors. In addition, certain lipid ratios like total cholesterol / HDL cholesterol and the LDL cholesterol/HDL cholesterol ratio also correlate with cardiovascular disease. The recommended ratios for the two are 3.5⁴²

HDL and LDL are two of the four main groups of plasma lipoproteins that are involved in lipid metabolism and the exchange of cholesterol, cholesterol ester and triglycerides between tissues^{43,44}

Some studies have shown an inverse correlation between plasma HDL levels and risk of cardiovascular disease, implying that factors associated with HDL protect against atherosclerosis. Some of these factors appear to have anti-oxidant and anti-inflammatory effects which may obviate processes that initiate atherogenesis.^{45,46} Epidemiological studies have also shown that elevated concentrations of total or LDL cholesterol in the blood are risk factors for coronary disease.⁴⁷

Most extra-hepatic tissues, although having a requirement for cholesterol, have low activity of the cholesterol biosynthetic pathway. Their cholesterol requirements are supplied by LDL, which is internalised by receptor-mediated endocytosis.

A major function of HDL cholesterol is to enhance reverse cholesterol transport by scavenging excess cholesterol from peripheral tissues

followed by esterification through lecithin:cholesterol acyltransferase and delivering it to the liver and steroidogenic organs for subsequent synthesis of bile acids and lipoproteins and eventual elimination from the body.^{48,49} This role of HDL has been shown to be responsible for its atheroprotective properties.

HDL cholesterol also regulates the exchange of proteins and lipids between various lipoproteins.⁵⁰ In addition, HDL provides the protein components required to activate lipoprotein lipase which releases fatty acids that can be oxidised by the - oxidation pathway to release energy.^{43,44} Most importantly, HDL can inhibit oxidation of LDL as well as the atherogenic effects of oxidised LDL by virtue of its antioxidant property.⁴⁹

In a prospective study on ocular manifestation of hyperlipoproteinemia, various ocular abnormalities like xanthelasma, arcus senilis and juvenilis, lipid keratopathy, iris xanthoma, lenticular opacities, drusen of macula, lipemia retinalis etc were documented.⁵¹

In another study to evaluate lenticular opacities in patients with underlying dyslipidaemia, it was found that cortical opacification was most prevalent sign of dyslipidaemia and occurred in relatively young age and cortical opacification should be regarded as an indicator for lipid profile evaluation.⁵²

Hypertension with dyslipidaemia can lead to complication and hence this study to evaluate the role of altered lipid profile on visual function in hypertensive patients.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

SOURCE OF DATA:

This study will be carried out on patients diagnosed to have essential hypertension attending / admitted to B.L.D.E.U'S Shri B.M.Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research centre, Bijapur from 1st October 2012- 31st March 2014.

METHOD OF COLLECTION OF DATA

Sample Size: The prevalence rate of hypertension is 5.9% in urban and 3.5 in rural among male population, 6.9% in urban and 3.5% in rural among female population.¹³

The total prevalence rate of hypertension is 19.8% approximated to 20%. Considering prevalence rate of hypertension 20%, at 95% confidence level and at ± 5 margin of error. The calculated sample size is 245.

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times p \times q}{d^2}$$

p =Prevalence

q = 100-p

d = margin of error.

Hence a minimum of 245 cases of hypertension will be included in the study.

Statistical analysis:

Data will be analyzed by following methods

1. Mean \pm SD
2. Statistical tests like 't' and X^2 tests.

Inclusion Criteria

Patients diagnosed to have essential hypertension according to JNC 7 classification will be included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients suffering from other diseases like Diabetes, HIV, syphilis, T.B, PIH, secondary hypertension, high myopes, and other retinal disease will be excluded from the study.
- Patients with ocular media haze in both eyes so as to interfere with a detailed examination of the fundus.

INVESTIGATIONS / INTERVENTIONS

- There are no animal experiments involved in this study.
- Blood glucose estimation, Complete blood profile
- Urine examination
- Fasting serum lipid profile.
- Other investigations like Blood urea, serum creatinine, Chest x-ray ECG ECHO, CT scan, abdominal USG will be done wherever required.

RESULTS

The present study “**A CROSS SECTIONAL STUDY OF ASSOCIATION OF FUNDUS MANIFESTATIONS WITH THE SERUM LIPID PROFILE IN HYPERTENSIVE PATIENTS.**” Conducted in BLDEA, Hospital and RC Bijapur in Shri B M Patil Medical College during the period of 1st October 2012- 31st March 2014. During this period after satisfying the selection criteria 245 patients were included in this study.

Off the 245 patients, 106(43.26%) patients had normal fundus and 139(56.73%) patients had retinopathy. The prevalence of retinopathy in this study is 56.73%. Among these patients 91 were males and 48 were females. With M: F= 1.9:1 with the age range of 25-85 years (Mean age of 57.16 years). And average duration of hypertension of 6.41 years.

TABLE 1. Prevalence of Hypertensive Retinopathy.

Hypertensive Retinopathy	No. of patients	
Normal	106 (43.26%)	
I	42	139 (56.73%)
II	61	
III	34	
IV	2	

Graph 1: Prevalance of Hypertensive Retinopathy

Table No. 2 : Retinopathy in Relation to Age Distribution.

Age	Normal	Grade I	Grade II	Grade III	Grade IV	Total
<30	4	0	0	1	0	5
31-40	17	3	2	0	0	22
41-50	26	6	4	3	1	40
51-60	43	16	19	9	1	88
>61	16	17	36	21	0	90
Total	102	42	61	33	2	245

$X^2=56.4; p<0.0001$

Among 245 patients studied, 5(2.04%) patients belong to <30 years age category among this 1(20%) patient had retinopathy and 4(80%) had no retinopathy. 22(8.97%) patients belong to 31-40 years age category. Of these 05(22.72%) had retinopathy whereas 17(77.27%) did not have retinopathy.

The next category consisting of 40(16.32%) patients belong to (41-50) years of age group of which 26(65%) showed no retinopathy, 14(35%) showed retinopathy.

Another category consisting of 88(35.91%) patients belonging to 51-60 years of age group. 45(51.13%) patients had retinopathy, while 43(48.86%) patients, had no retinopathy.

In the last category that is above 60 years had 90(36.73%) patients, of which 74(82%) had retinopathy and 16(17.77%) had no retinopathy. Over all there was statistically significant relation found with age distribution.

Graph 2. Retinopathy in Relation to Age Distribution

Table No. 3: Retinopathy in Relation to Sex Distribution

SEX	RETINOPATHY	NO RETINOPATHY	TOTAL
MALE	91	73	164
FEMALE	48	33	81
TOTAL	139	106	245

$X^2=0.314$; $p=0.57$

There were 164 (66.93%) males and 81 (33.06%) females in our study group. Out of which 91(65.46%) males and 48(34.53%) females had retinopathy. The remaining 73(68.86%) males and 33(31.13%) females had no retinopathy respectively. There was no statistical significance.

Graph 3. Retinopathy in relation to sex distribution.

Table 4 : Relationship between Retinopathy and Duration of Hypertension

Grade of Retinopathy	Duration of Hypertension (Yrs)				Total
	0-5	6-10	11-15	>15	
Normal	92	14	00	00	106
I	19	20	03	00	42
II	19	25	13	04	61
III	06	11	09	07	34
IV	00	00	01	00	02
TOTAL	136	71	26	11	245

$$X^2 = 56.5; P < 0.001$$

Of 245 patients, 136 patients had hypertension since 0-5 years. Of which 44 had retinopathy of varying degrees, while 92 had no retinopathy. 71 patients were in 6-10 years, of which 14 patients had no retinopathy, while 57 patients had retinopathy.

Next group of 26 patients, had hypertension since 11-15 years, of which 26(100%) patients had retinopathy.

Among the last group of 11 patients who had hypertension since > 15 years, 11(100%) had retinopathy. Overall, the relationship between various grades of retinopathy and duration was statistically significant (p<0.0001).

Graph 4. Relationship between Retinopathy and Duration of Hypertension.

Table 5: Showing Relationship of Retinopathy with Serum Total Cholesterol

Grades of hypertension	Serum total cholesterol levels (mg/dl)			
	<200	200-239	>240	Total
Normal	88	12	06	106
I	34	07	01	42
II	37	15	09	61
III	16	09	09	34
IV	00	01	01	02
Total	175	44	26	245

$X^2 = 31.5; P < 0.001$

Out of 245 patients, 175(71.42%) had total serum cholesterol within normal limits (< 200 mg /dl). of which 87(49.71%) patients had retinopathy, while 88(50.28%) patients had no retinopathy. The next group of 44(17.95%) patients had total serum cholesterol between (200-239 mg/dl) which is considered to be borderline. Of which 32(72.72%) patients had retinopathy while 12(27.27%) had no retinopathy.

The last group of 26(10.61%) patients had serum total cholesterol levels of >240 which is considered to be abnormal. Of which 20(76.92%) patients had retinopathy, 6(23.07%) had no retinopathy. Overall the increase in total serum cholesterol levels correlated well with increasing severity of retinopathy ($p < 0.0001$).

Graph 5. Showing Relationship of Retinopathy with Serum Total Cholesterol.

Table No. 6: Showing Relationship of Serum LDL Cholesterol with Retinopathy

Retinopathy	Serum LDL cholesterol (mg / dl) ⁵⁶			TOTAL
	< 130 (Normal)	130.159 (Borderline)	> 160 (Abnormal)	
Normal	86	10	10	106
I	38	02	02	42
II	33	12	16	61
III	16	04	14	34
IV	00	00	02	02
TOTAL	173	28	44	245

$$X^2 = 47.7; P < 0.001$$

Out of 245 patients studied. 173(70.61%) had serum LDL cholesterol levels of < 130 mg / dl (normal). Of which 86(49.71%) had no retinopathy while 87(50.28%) had retinopathy of varying grades.

The next group of 28(11.42%) had serum LDL cholesterol levels between (130-159) mg / dl (borderline) of which 10(35.71%) had no retinopathy, while 18(64.28%) had retinopathy.

The last group of 44 (17.95%) patients had serum LDL cholesterol levels of > 160 mg / dl (abnormal) of which 10(22.72%) patients had no retinopathy, while 34(77.27%) had retinopathy.

Overall, the increasing level of serum LDL – cholesterol showed statistically significant correlation with the grades of hypertensive retinopathy (p<0.0001).

Graph 6. Showing Relationship of Serum LDL Cholesterol with Retinopathy

Table 7 : Showing Relationship between Serum HDL- Cholesterol with Retinopathy

Grades of Hypertension	Serum HDL cholesterol (mg/dl)			
	>60	36-60	<35	Total
Normal	01	56	49	106
I	01	26	15	42
II	00	39	22	61
III	00	24	10	34
IV	00	01	01	02
Total	02	146	97	245

$X^2 = 6.31; P = 0.612$

Out of 245 patients, 2 (0.81%) patient had serum HDL-cholesterol levels of >60mg / dl, among which 1 had retinopathy and 1 had no retinopathy.

The next group of 146(59.59%) had serum HDL – cholesterol levels between 36-60 ml/dl (borderline) of which 56(38.35%) patients had no retinopathy, whereas 90(61.64%) patients had retinopathy.

The last group of 97(39.59%) patients had serum HDL-C levels of < 35 gm/dl (abnormal) of which 49(50.51%) patients had no retinopathy, while 48(49.48%) had retinopathy.

Overall there was no statistically significant relation between the serum levels of HDL – cholesterol and the grades of retinopathy (p=0.612).

Graph 7. Showing Relationship between Serum HDL- Cholesterol with Retinopathy.

Table 8 : Showing Relationship of Serum Triglycerides with Retinopathy

Retinopathy	Serum TG levels(mg/dl)		
	<150	>150	Total
Normal	90	16	106
I	26	16	42
II	32	29	61
III	14	20	34
IV	02	00	02
Total	164	81	245

$X^2 = 32.9$; $P < 0.001$

Out of 245 patients, 164(66.93%) patients had serum triglycerides levels of < 150mg/dl (normal), of which 90(54.87%) patients had no retinopathy whereas 74(45.12%) patients had retinopathy.

In the remaining 81(33.06%) patients who had serum triglycerides levels of > 150 mg/dl 65(80.24%) patients had retinopathy, whereas 16(19.75%) patients did not.

Overall, serum triglycerides levels correlated positively with increasing severity of retinopathy which was statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$).

Graph 8. Showing Relationship of Serum Triglycerides with Retinopathy

TABLE 9. SHOWING RELATION OF RAISED LDL AND TRIGLYCERIDE WITH RETINOPATHY.

Retinopathy	LDL>160 (TG<150)	TRIGLYCERIDE >150 (LDL<130)	LDL>160, TG>150	TOTAL
NORMAL	06	12	4	22
GRADE I	01	14	01	16
GRADE II	07	13	08	28
GRADE III	07	09	07	23
GRADE IV	02	00	00	02
TOTAL	23	48	20	91

$X^2 = 16.4; P = 0.037$

Out of 245 patients, 23(9.38%) patients had LDL>160 mg/dl with TG < 150 mg/dl. Among them 6(26.08%) patients had no retinopathy and 17(73.91%) had retinopathy.

In the next group of TG> 150mg/dl and LDL<130 mg/dl, there were 48(19.59%) patients. 12(25%) had no retinopathy, 36 (75%) had retinopathy.

In the last group of 20(8.16%) patients (LDL>160,TG>150) 04(20%) had no retinopathy, 16(80%) had retinopathy.

Over all there was statistical significance with individual raised levels of LDL, TG and both (P<0.05).

GRAPH 9. SHOWING RELATION OF RAISED LDL AND TRIGLYCERIDE WITH RETINOPATHY

DISCUSSION

A total of 245 patients were included in the study who were diagnosed to have primary essential hypertension. They were divided into retinopathy group and no retinopathy group initially further retinopathy patients were divided depending on the severity of the retinopathy into Grade I, II, III & IV.

The mean age of patients in present study population was 57.16 years ranging from 25-96 years. Out of 245 patients, 139 belonged to retinopathy group with mean age of 61.66 ± 11.07 years, remaining 106 patients had normal fundus, with mean age of 51.77 ± 11.51 years. ($p < 0.0001$)

Epidemiologic studies show that signs of hypertensive retinopathy are common in people 40 years of age or older. Prevalence rates ranged from 2 to 15 percent for various signs of retinopathy^{25 - 27}

The higher rates of prevalence in these more recent studies are probably due to a higher sensitivity of photography, as compared with clinical ophthalmoscopy, for detecting certain signs of retinopathy.⁴

There were 164 males and 81 females in our study group, out of which 91(65.46%) males and 48(34.53%) females had retinopathy. 73(68.86%) males and 33(31.13%) females had no retinopathy respectively, there was no significant sex preponderance ($p=0.57$)

Variations in the prevalence of specific signs of hypertensive retinopathy according to age and sex have not been consistently demonstrated.^{25 - 27} There have been fewer studies of the incidence of hypertensive retinopathy. Two studies indicate that the incidence of various signs of retinopathy over a period of five to seven years ranges from 6 to 10 percent.^{28,53}

Blood pressure

In the present study mean diastolic BP was 90.64 ± 16.91 mm of Hg in retinopathy group and 82.18 ± 12.57 mm Hg in No retinopathy group, which was statistically significant.

Mean systolic BP in retinopathy group 147.59 ± 28.11 and in No retinopathy group it was 130.79 ± 22.72 , shows statistical significant.

The mean duration of hypertension was 6.41 years was observed in total study population. Patients with retinopathy had mean duration of hypertension of 8.78 years, patients with No retinopathy had 3.17 years.

Numerous studies have confirmed the strong association between the presence of signs of hypertensive retinopathy and elevated blood pressure.^{25 - 29} Two studies have further evaluated the effect of a history of elevated blood pressure on the occurrence of specific retinal signs.^{30,31} In both studies, generalized retinal arteriolar narrowing and arteriovenous nicking were associated with an elevation in blood pressure that had been documented six to eight years before the retinal assessment; the studies were controlled for concurrent blood-pressure levels.

This association suggests that generalized narrowing and arteriovenous nicking are markers of vascular damage from chronic hypertension. In contrast, other signs (focal arteriolar narrowing, retinal hemorrhages, microaneurysms, and cotton-wool spots) were related to current but not previous blood-pressure levels^{30,31} and may therefore be more indicative of the severity of recent hypertension.

Furthermore, the observation of signs of retinopathy in people without a known history of hypertension suggests that these signs may be markers of a prehypertensive state. For example, generalized and focal narrowing of the retinal arterioles has been shown to predict the risk of hypertension in normotensive

persons.⁵¹ other factors unrelated to hypertension³¹ (e.g., hyperglycemia, inflammation, and endothelial dysfunction) may also be involved in the pathogenesis of retinopathy.

Serum lipids

In recent years there have been many studies demonstrating a correlation between increased arterial blood pressure and altered lipid profiles, and there has been an especially positive correlation between high cholesterol levels and blood pressure.⁵⁵

More than 35 years ago, it was noticed that about two-thirds of patients with atherosclerotic retinal changes had atherosclerotic changes of other arteries as well and *vice versa*.^{56 - 58} However, the studies did not determine serum lipids and apoproteins in these patients. The arteries analyzed by ophthalmoscopy (branches of the central retina

artery) do have all the layers (endothelium–intima, basement membrane, media with smooth muscle cells, and adventitia) and resemble small arteries in other organs, including heart and brain.⁵⁹ Arterioles with the diameter smaller than 63 and 134 μm lack internal elastic lamina and continuous layer of smooth muscle cells.^{60,61}

In our study the patients with retinopathy had mean serum lipid profiles as follows; Total cholesterol 201, LDL-cholesterol 125.47, HDL-cholesterol 37.79, and that of Serum Triglycerides being 169.71. And those with normal fundus had mean serum lipid levels as follows: Total cholesterol 172.09, LDL-cholesterol 103.15, HDL-cholesterol 36.69, and that of Serum Triglycerides being 116.11.

In general the association of serum total cholesterol levels was highly significant ($p < 0.0001$). Similarly we found a significant association of serum LDL-Cholesterol and the severity of the retinopathy, ($p < 0.0001$).

The mean serum HDL-Cholesterol values for retinopathy group were 38.68 & that for no retinopathy group was 39. There was no significant association of the serum HDL-Cholesterol & the retinopathy.

Although overall association of serum triglycerides was found to be significant with retinopathy ($p < 0.0001$).

Change in lipid parameters is associated with changes in the retinal arteries correspond and more or associated with coronary artery atherosclerosis, suggesting once again that atherosclerosis is often a generalized process. Studies have shown that, when end organ vascular damage is an issue, multi-organ involvement is the rule rather than the exception⁶² despite the indications that susceptibility to vascular damage of the vascular walls does not seem to be either synchronous or uniform in different areas.

CONCLUSION

Our study showed significant association between serum lipid parameters and hypertensive retinopathy.

Dyslipidaemia is already considered as an important risk factors for end organ failure. For severity of retinopathy dyslipidaemia can be considered a risk factor.

We can conclude that routine ophthalmological check-up of hypertensive patient is must. In patients with signs of hypertensive retinopathy further evaluation of lipid profile helps in early detection and treatment of risk factors. This may be helpful in preventing blindness as well as cardiovascular morbidity and mortality.

SUMMARY

Hypertension is an important worldwide public-health challenge because of its high frequency and concomitant risks of cardiovascular and kidney disease. This trend seems to be associated with socio economic and life style changes.

Studies have shown the brain, heart, eyes and the kidneys are most likely to be affected due to persistent elevation of arterial pressure and increased peripheral resistance. Systemic hypertension also affects the arteries, veins, choroid and the optic nerve in the eyes.

However the effects and many complications of hypertension may be delayed and can be prevented by prompt and effective treatment.

Our study denoted the relationship of dyslipdemia and fundus changes in hypertension. 245 patients having essential hypertension were screened for retinopathy changes. A major proportion amounting to 139(56.73%) patients had retinopathy whereas rest 106(43.26%) had no retinopathy .Subjects having retinopathy were mainly concentrated in the 6th decade (88 patients, 35.91%) and over 60 years who were 90 patients(36.73%). Thus showing increasing prevalence of hypertensive retinopathy with increasing age.

No sex preponderance towards developing retinopathy was found in our study (p=0.57).

As regards to the duration of the disease; the prevalence of retinopathy definitely increased with increasing duration. All patients having hypertension for more than 10 years had retinopathy.

Our study showed that hypertensive retinopathy and its overall prevalence bears definite positive correlation with total cholesterol(p<0.0001); LDL cholesterol (p<0.0001), serum triglycerides (p<0.0001).

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ANNEXURE-I

ETHICAL CLEARANCE

B.L.D.E. UNIVERSITY'S
SHRI.B.M.PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, BIJAPUR-586 103
INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL COMMITTEE

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

The Ethical Committee of this college met on 18-10-12 at 3-30pm to scrutinize the Synopsis of Postgraduate Students of this college from Ethical Clearance point of view. After scrutiny the following original/corrected & revised version synopsis of the Thesis has been accorded Ethical Clearance.

Title A cross sectional study of association of fundus manifestations with the serum lipid profile in hypertensive patients

Name of P.G. student Dr. Shravan Naraykar
Ophthalmology

Name of Guide/Co-investigator Dr. M. H. Dabil
prof. ophthalmology

DR. TEJASWINI VALLABHA
CHAIRMAN
INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL COMMITTEE
BLDEU'S, SHRI.B.M.PATIL
MEDICAL COLLEGE, BIJAPUR.

Following documents were placed before E.C. for Scrutinization

- 1) Copy of Synopsis/Research project.
- 2) Copy of informed consent form.
- 3) Any other relevant documents.

ANNEXURE-II

SAMPLE INFORMED CONSENT FORM:

TITLE OF PROJECT: “A CROSS SECTIONAL STUDY OF ASSOCIATION OF FUNDUS MANIFESTATIONS WITH THE SERUM LIPID PROFILE IN HYPERTENSIVE PATIENTS.”

GUIDE : DR.M.H.PATIL

PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR : DR. SHRAVAN MASURKAR

PURPOSE OF RESEARCH

I have been informed that this study will analyse association between serum lipid parameters and hypertensive retinopathy.

PROCEDURE

I am aware that in addition to routine care received and I will be asked series of questions by the investigations.I have been asked to undergo the necessary investigation,which will help the investigator as a part of routine management.

RISKS AND DISCOMFORT

I understand that I may experience some pain and discomfort during the examination or during my treatment. This is mainly the result of my condition and the procedures of this study are not expected to these feeling which are associated with the usual course of treatment.

BENEFITS

I understand that my participation in this study will help to analyze association between serum lipid parameters and hypertensive retinopathy.

CONFIDENTIALITY

I understand that medical information procedure by this study will become a part of my Hospital records and will be subject to the confidentiality and privacy regulation of the said hospital information of a sensitive personal nature will not be a part of the medical records, but will be stored in the investigators research file and identified only by a code number. The code key connecting name to numbers will be kept in a separate secure location.

If the data are used for publication in the medical literature or for teaching purposes no names will be used and other identifiers such as photographs and videotapes or audio will be used only with my special written permission . I understand I may see the photographs and videotapes and hear the audiotapes before giving this permission.

REQUEST FOR MORE INFORMATION

I understand that i may ask more questions about the study at any time. **Dr Shравan Masurkar** is available to answer my questions or concerns. I understand that I will be informed of any significant new findings discovered during the course of this study, which might influence my continued participation.

If during the study, or later, I wish to discuss my participation in or concerns regarding this study with a person not directly involved, I am aware that the social worker of the hospital is available to talk with me. A copy of this consent form will be given to me to keep for careful reading.

REFUSAL OR WITHDRAWAL OR PARTICIPATION

I understand that my participation is voluntary and I may refuse to participate or may withdraw consent and discontinue participation in the study at any time without prejudice to my present of future care at this hospital. I also understand that

Dr. Shravan Masurkar may terminate my participate in this study at any time after he has explained the reasons for doing so and has helped arrange for my continued care by my own physician or physical therapist, if this is appropriate.

INJURY STATEMENT

I understand that in the unlikely event of injury to me resulting directly from my participation in this, if such injury were reported promptly, then medical treatment would be available to me, but no further compensation would be provided. I understand that by my agreement to participate in this study I am not waiving any of my legal rights.

I have explained (patients/relevant name)the purpose of the research, the procedures risks and benefits to the best of my ability in patients own language.

Investigator:

Date:

I confirm that **Dr. Shravan Masurkar** has explained to me the research ,the procedure that I will undergo, and the possible risks and discomforts as well as benefits that I may experience. I have read and I understand this consent form. Therefore I agree to give my consent to participate as a subject in this research project.

Participant / Guardian:

Date:

Witness to signature:

Date:

ANNEXURE-III
CASE SHEETPROFORMA

Name:

Date:

Age/Sex:

O.P.No./I.P.NO

Occupation/Education/Marital status/Rural/Urban:

DOA:

DOD:

Address:

Socio Economic Status:

History of presenting complaints:

General complaints:

Giddiness

Blurring of vision.

Headache

Ocular Symptomatology:

Past history :

History of similar complaints

History of ocular diseases

History of Hypertension/Diabetes/STD's/PTB

Treatment history:

Family History

1. Diabetes mellitus

2. Hypertension

3. Ocular disease

Personal History

1. Smoking Yes/No/Stopped Since

2. Alcohol Yes/No/Stopped Since

3. Tobacco Yes/No/Stopped Since

General Examination : Built Weight

Pallor Clubbing

Icterus Cyanosis

Lymphadenopathy

Vital Data : Pulse Temperature

BP RR

Indirect ophthalmoscopy

Anterior segment photograph

Fundus photograph

Investigations

Blood test

Hb

TC

DC

ESR

RBS

Urine:

Sugar

Albumin

Microscopic

Lipid profile:

Total cholesterol

LDL

HDL

VLDL

Triglycerides

LDL: HDL

Other investigations

Diagnosis:

ANNEXURE-IV

KEYS TO MASTER CHART

FBS	-	FASTING BLOOD SUGAR
HDL	-	HIGH DENSITY LIPOPROTEIN
LDL	-	LOW DENSITY LIPOPROTEIN
TG	-	TRIGLYCERIDE
BCVA	-	BEST CORRECTED VISUAL ACUITY
IOL	-	INTRA OCULAR LENS
CAT	-	CATARACT
PTER	-	PTERYGIUM
NS	-	NUCLEAR SCLEROSIS
PSC	-	POSTERIOR SUBCAPSULAR CATARACT
Y	-	YES
N	-	NO
OD	-	OCULUS DEXTER
OS	-	OCULUS SINISTER

ANNEXURE-V

GRADE I

GRADE II

Grade III

GRADE IV

61	Yellappa Jadav	55	F	159863	9	170	100	98	239	42	136	307	Y	CF1MT	6/9,N6	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RAPD	RRR	N	N	II
62	Subash Jorapur	56	M	159905	7	160	90	104	215	52	38	127	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	I
63	Kallappa Matur	52	M	160088	15	150	90	104	208	44	112	133	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	I
64	Bhupal Mandapur	56	M	158793	5	160	90	99	186	55	89	78	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
65	Ashima Jain	40	M	158938	0	160	90	106	223	28	188	134	Y	PL,PR	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RAPD	RRR	N	N	II
66	Maruthi Gujnal	51	F	159133	6	160	100	96	201	45	91	111	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	I
67	Vittal Patil	44	M	157700	5	130	90	102	167	32	81	172	Y	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	PTER	PTER	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	I
68	Neela Gomadi	45	M	158177	4	150	90	103	160	32	70	92	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
69	Ninganagouda Patil	45	F	156823	4	140	90	104	179	43	110	128	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
70	Mangilal Jain	42	M	157046	5	140	90	92	158	30	96	108	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
71	Sambojirao More	65	M	109942	16	200	100	106	220	32	189	198	Y	6/12,N8	6/12,N9	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT,	III
72	machibai Jain	45	M	160261	5	190	120	108	162	24	56	110	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	I
73	Leelavathi Ratnoji	72	F	160773	7	150	90	105	194	68	110	80	N	6/18,N10	6/60,N24	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	I
74	Veena Kamath	55	F	162190	4	142	92	94	198	43	167	138	Y	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
75	Lingappa Bhumadgi	55	F	160283	5	130	94	102	185	13	128	219	Y	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	I
76	Arun Potdar	65	M	162935	0	140	90	102	160	38	78	78	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
77	Laxmibai Kuradi	58	M	162603	0	150	94	93	186	32	70	65	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
78	Sudhir	55	F	162848	4	150	100	102	185	32	135	136	Y	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
79	Appaji Ramgouda	38	M	41752	0	140	92	103	177	33	110	170	Y	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
80	Sharifa Tenginkeri	63	M	158140	4	150	90	92	162	38	80	78	Y	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
81	Shivangouda Patil	60	F	162540	5	140	90	106	198	42	110	126	Y	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
82	Sridevi	59	M	119961	4	140	92	92	163	32	78	87	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
83	Ashok keragol	45	F	120415	4	140	90	90	191	29	110	87	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
84	Arun Gurade	58	M	133408	8	140	96	90	201	24	188	145	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	III
85	Shankar Naik	40	M	131446	7	200	180	98	167	39	108	259	Y	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	I
86	Parwathi Balekundri	70	M	121888	4	140	90	102	173	30	67	188	Y	6/9,N8	6/12,N8	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	IRR,SLUG	IOL	IOL	N
87	Kadappa Hanchinal	73	F	165005	15	160	70	102	187	28	192	86	N	CFCF	6/24,N12	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT,	III
88	Amarsingh Lamba	65	M	164335	9	170	80	96	214	37	65	59	N	6/6,N6	6/60,N18	N	N	PTER	PT	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	CAT,	II
89	Prakash Bhaskar Gerkal	42	M	163050	8	150	90	108	196	26	123	283	Y	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	III
90	Laxmibai Patil	51	M	163162	13	160	100	92	230	36	203	87	Y	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	IV
91	Baswaraj Patted	65	F	164973	5	120	90	105	168	54	89	67	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
92	Ramesh	62	M	165011	6	130	90	101	239	24	133	319	Y	6/9,N6	CF1/2MT	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	SLUG	N	N	III
93	Apasab Tavadare	56	M	165212	11	180	110	86	208	35	198	91	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	II
94	Babasaheb Sharbidri	60	M	145600	6	200	110	86	207	46	101	68	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	PTER	PTER	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
95	Giri Pikle	42	M	146477	4	150	90	92	189	42	107	150	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
96	Kalangouda B Patil	85	M	146490	30	150	90	106	226	36	126	436	Y	CF5MT	6/18P,N18	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT,	III
97	Mallawwa	62	M	165223	6	130	90	96	191	56	99	88	N	6/9,N6	NOPL	N	N	N		arcus	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	II
98	Mohammed Sharif	60	F	165215	5	130	92	92	186	25	101	120	N	6/9,N6	6/9,N6	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT,	N
99	Suryakanth	56	M	165219	4	140	82	96	172	38	158	256	Y	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	III
100	sheela	54	M	165320	4	130	94	104	163	44	82	99	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
101	Hanamantaraya	60	F	9718	1	170	100	129	155	31	103	105	N	6/18,N6	6/18,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	II
102	HIRU RATHOD	82	m	9721	7	150	120	144	175	53	101	102	N	CF 6	CF 6	N	N	N	N	ARCUS	ARCUS	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	II
103	SUMAN	42	M	10265	0	130	90	97	103	36	51	79	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
104	RAFEQ	65	M	26367	30	134	90	131	263	44	112	497	Y	CF2M	CF 6M	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	IOL	III
105	MAHADEV	60	M	28183	2	180	100	100	212	45	150	83	N	CF4M	CF4M	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	N
106	kalavati	55	M	28185	5	120	92	75	135	30	87.6	87	N	6/36,N6	6/36,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT,	N
107	SHARANAGOUDA	38	F	11242	1	116	70	97	189	77	105	218	Y	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
108	SADASHIV	58	M	11243	5	130	80	135	333	37	239.3	257	Y	6/36,N6	6/36,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	CAT,	III
109	SHAKARAPPA	58	M	12263	3	110	70	138	150	21	71	190	Y	6/24,N6	6/24,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	II
110	NEELKHANT	64	M	12367	10	120	94	217	286	46	207.6	190	Y	6/36,N6	6/36,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	III
111	SHANKARGOUDA	52	M	12398	4	170	80	154	184	29	98	285	Y	6/24,N6	6/24,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT	II
112	Hanamantaraya	28	M	12409	1	156	100	83	262	46	112.6	517	Y	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	III
113	HUCHHAPPA	66	M	13466	10	130	80	127	197	44	96.8	287	Y	6/36,N6	6/36,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	III
114	DHANABAI	50	M	8568	3	90	60	121	125	22	90	65	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
115	RAMAJI	65	F	8817	2	120	80	119	153	42	92	93	N	CF4M	CF4M	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	N
116	GANGAPPA	60	M	13508	3	120	70	131	146	37	81.4	138	N	6/36,N6	6/36,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	N
117	SABU	55	M	8566	4	118	70	107	206	34	155.8	81	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	N
118	MANAPPA	51	M	6637	5	120	70	103	155	35	100.2	99	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
119	LAXMIBAI	45	M	6615	3	110	70	100	130	30	86.8	66	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
120	BASAVARAJ	40	F	6592	4	120	70	120	165	30	111.4	118	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
121	HANMANTH	65	M	6189	7	160	90	118	176	25	127.4	129	N	6/36,N6	6/36,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT	II
122	GANGAPPA	60	M	13508	3	120	70	131	146	37	81.4	138	N	6/3														

187	MADHURABAI	60	M	7233	2	142	110	91	215	34	130	254	Y	6/9,N6	6/9,N6	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	N
188	SITABAI	65	F	7351	3	142	80	139	230	42	168.4	123	Y	CF5M	CF5M	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT	N
189	SONABAI	50	F	8038	4	90	64	194	229	41	167.4	103	Y	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
190	RAJASAB	60	F	9278	6	170	110	141	145	31	93	103	N	6/9,N10	6/9,N10	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT	I
191	HOTRAPPA	65	M	9585	8	123	60	211	170	25	105	200	Y	CF5M	CF5M	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT	I
192	GOVIND	62	M	10357	5	130	90	189	264	40	168	176	Y	CF5M	CF5M	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT	II
193	ABDULLA	62	M	10695	4	150	90	156	165	38	77.4	248	Y	6/9,N10	6/9,N10	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	II
194	ARJUN	57	M	10799	3	130	80	100	166	29	96	204	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT	N
195	Prakash	66	M	10907	6	110	80	123	155	45	94	78	N	CF4M	CF4M	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT	N
196	KALLAPPA	26	M	10915	0	140	90	107	165	35	109.4	103	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
197	PAVADAPPA	55	M	11100	6	140	90	219	209	42	23	720	Y	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	III
198	MAHALINGAWWA	57	M	11226	4	120	60	181	145	39	92	69	N	6/9,N10	6/9,N10	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT	N
199	IRRAPPA	62	F	13594	10	120	80	137	180	29	126.4	133	N	CF4M	CF4M	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT	II
200	CHANDAMMA	43	M	12412	3	118	80	101	134	38	72.2	119	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
201	CHANDRAWWA YETMANI	80	F	10432	15	114	60	104	278	38	197.6	213	Y	CF4M	CF4M	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	III
202	LAXMIBAI TUMBAGI	70	F	10177	10	150	92	181	180	58	98.2	159	N	CF3M	CF3M	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	CAT	III
203	SHANKARAMMA	65	F	10143	5	160	90	152	231	52	146.6	162	Y	6/9,N10	6/9,N10	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT	II
204	TUBIRAM	60	F	7491	4	110	70	100	130	30	86	66	N	6/9,N10	6/9,N10	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT	N
205	RAMESH	60	M	7067	3	160	70	122	153	42.8	94	93	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT	N
206	GURULING	58	M	7004	2	110	70	91	139	36	75	141	N	6/9,N6	6/9,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	CAT	N
207	SANKAPPAGOUDA	38	M	20414	5	110	80	121	144	42	88.2	81	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
208	NIJALINGAPPA	62	M	20398	6	156	100	150	312	30	203	190	Y	CF4M	CF4M	N	N	N	N	ARCUS	ARCUS	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	II
209	MARUTI	60	M	19318	7	126	90	111	195	32	101	280	Y	CF5M	CF5M	N	N	N	N	ARCUS	ARCUS	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT	I
210	MD.ALI	68	M	17780	3	120	80	133	153	36	71	225	Y	CF4M	CF4M	N	N	N	N	ARCUS	ARCUS	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	II
211	VASANTH	72	M	1751	10	140	120	93	200	29	120	144	N	CF3M	CF3M	N	N	N	N	ARCUS	ARCUS	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	I
212	DEVAKAWWA	69	M	1732	5	142	96	96	210	30	125	211	Y	CF4M	CF4M	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	I
213	SHREDEVI	60	F	17289	6	110	70	189	250	40	114	176	Y	6/9,N6	6/9,N6	N	N	N	N	ARCUS	ARCUS	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT	N
214	SIDDANNA	46	F	17172	2	140	60	104	182	42	108	101	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
215	CHANNAMALLAYA	38	M	16827	2	140	90	106	165	35	26.6	103	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
216	BAPU PATIL	40	M	16812	4	110	70	133	256	40	162.8	166	Y	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
217	PHOOLSING RATHOD	68	M	16678	10	110	80	130	185	45	94	178	Y	CF5M	CF5M	N	N	N	N	ARCUS	ARCUS	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	II
218	KAMLAWWA	50	M	15380	3	110	70	100	194	40	106	101	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
219	SITABAI	80	F	14186	8	140	110	180	201	35	118	203	Y	CF5M	CF5M	N	N	N	N	ARCUS	ARCUS	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	N
220	MAHANTAMMA	75	F	14606	5	140	60	130	150	30	85	98	N	6/60,N10	6/60,N10	N	N	N	N	ARCUS	ARCUS	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	N
221	MUKTABAI	45	F	14589	2	130	90	139	150	31	86.2	91	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
222	MALLANGOUDA	76	F	14130	5	150	90	176	200	28	172	101	N	CF5M	CF5M	N	N	N	N	ARCUS	ARCUS	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	II
223	DUNDAPPA	60	M	13076	3	120	80	116	150	39	79	165	N	6/36,N10	6/36,N10	N	N	N	N	ARCUS	ARCUS	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	I
224	SHRIKANTH	60	M	14413	5	150	100	168	248	30	176	210	Y	6/36,N10	6/18,N10	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT	N
225	MAHADEVI	55	M	14533	3	90	60	148	209	39	158	59	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT	N
226	BHARATI	60	F	14553	8	120	90	108	229	41	166	108	Y	6/36,N10	6/36,N10	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT	N
227	SONABAI	36	F	11252	0	110	80	106	200	31	151	128	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
228	MADUBABU	72	F	15883	8	120	70	150	163	32	84	159	Y	6/24,N10	6/24,N10	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT	I
229	NEELAWWA	50	M	10098	4	120	90	153	122	38	71	62	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
230	SAJABAI	96	F	9815	15	150	60	177	200	40	120	180	Y	CF3M	CF3M	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	II
231	SURESH	65	F	9732	5	140	70	120	150	30	80	121	N	6/36,N10	6/36,N10	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	I
232	SUMANTH	30	M	9180	2	90	60	121	145	32	23	75	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
233	SHIVANAND	70	M	8968	8	120	90	96	225	30	165	150	N	6/36,N10	6/36,N10	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT	I
234	GURURAJ	80	M	8480	11	120	70	97	170	32	80.4	145	N	6/24,N10	6/24,N10	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	II
235	SHANTAPPA	65	M	8121	9	150	90	127	253	42	132	193	Y	6/36,N10	6/36,N10	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT	II
236	RANGAPPA	56	M	15902	4	130	90	111	149	32	85	87	N	6/24,N10	6/24,N10	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT	N
237	KRISHNA	75	M	15944	7	150	80	85	220	38	162	98	Y	CF3M	CF3M	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	N
238	SHANKAR	51	M	15685	4	110	80	135	135	30	82	111	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
239	GANGABAI	37	M	15969	1	120	80	101	96	19	56	182	Y	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
240	SIDDANAGOUDA	80	F	17189	6	150	100	167	191	37	120	138	N	CF3M	CF3M	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	N
241	ADAMANH	36	M	17346	2	140	90	125	200	36	116	148	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N
242	LAXMIBAI	65	M	17615	6	150	100	127	262	46	112	517	Y	CF3M	CF3M	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT	III
243	BASSAMMA	70	F	18413	10	120	80	131	180	37	87	130	N	6/36,N10	6/36,N10	N	N	N	N	arcus	arcus	N	N	RRR	RRR	IOL	IOL	I
244	NINGAWWA	65	F	18578	6	140	80	140	149	35	90	135	N	6/36,N10	6/36,N10	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	CAT	CAT	N
245	RAMANAGOUDA	55	M	17564	4	150	90	123	150	32	66	150	N	6/6,N6	6/6,N6	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	RRR	RRR	N	N	N